

MECHANICAL PROPERTY CHARACTERIZATION OF A POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITE REINFORCED BY GRAPHITIC NANOFIBERS WITH REACTIVE LINKER

Wei Hong Zhong, * L. Roy Xu⁺, Vikram Bhamidipati⁺, Jiang Li* and Charles M. Lukehart*

**Department of Chemistry⁺ Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering
Vanderbilt Institute for Nano-scale Science and Engineering
Vanderbilt University
Nashville, TN 37235, USA*

ABSTRACT: Experiments to characterize mechanical properties of nano-fiber reinforced composites have been performed. Optimized processing methods have been used for the formation of derivatized graphitic carbon nanofiber (GCNF)/epoxy nanocomposites containing GCNFs with bifunctional hexanediamine linker molecules (GCNF-HDA) highly dispersed throughout the epoxy matrix. GCNF-HDA nanofibers are dispersed in both diluted epoxy (DER 324, Dow Comp.) and pure epoxy resin (Epon 828) at fiber loading of 0.3wt% using ultrasonication prior to thermal processing. Effects of sonication power and duration on the quality of the GCNF-HDA/epoxy composite materials have been determined from flexural and tensile property measurements and SEM/TEM imaging. Fracture toughness tests of Single Edge Notch Bending (SENB) specimens were also carried out. Results show that there was only a slight increase in mechanical properties of the nanocomposites.

KEYWORDS: nanocomposites, mechanical properties, carbon nanofiber, epoxy, ultrasonication.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibers are widely used as reinforcements for advanced polymeric matrix composites in many high-technology applications because of their high specific stiffness, strength and excellent electrical and thermal properties. Graphitic carbon nanofibers (GCNFs) are attractive additives for fabricating carbon fiber/polymer composite materials of enhanced mechanical property and electrical conductivity due to their unusual atomic structure. Many studies show that efficient wetting and high dispersion of carbon nanofibers within a polymer matrix continues is difficult to achieve [1-8]. Greatly enhanced performance of nanocomposite materials reinforced with nanotube or nanofiber as additives has not been fully achieved because of difficulties in achieving efficient dispersion and wetting of the nanoscale component within the matrix material, even when using surface-functionalized additives [6-14].

Chemical modification of carbon fiber surfaces was used to augment attractive interactions at the fiber/polymer interface. In the present study, the fabrication of GCNF/epoxy hybrid nanocomposites using GCNFs surface-derivatized with hexanediamine (GCNF-HDA) to reinforce an epoxy resin. Processing conditions have been optimized to give a hybrid material containing derivatized carbon nanofibers highly dispersed within the epoxy matrix. Ultrasonic methods [15], including low-power sonication using an ultrasonic cleaner and high-power sonication using a commercial sonifier, are investigated as a means to disperse GCNF-HDA nanofibers in the epoxy resin. The dispersion quality of the resulting hybrid nanocomposite is assessed through mechanical test results. The quality of the nanofiber dispersion within the epoxy resin was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The degree of wetting and adhesion at the nanofiber/epoxy resin interface was analyzed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM).

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Synthesis of GCNFs and Surface-Derivatized GCNFs with Hexanediamine (GCNF-HDA)

Herringbone-type carbon nanofibers were grown by the interaction of a carbon source gas with mixed-metal powder growth catalyst, following a modified literature procedure [16]. Detailed procedures on synthesis of herringbone GCNFs and GCNF-HDA were described in [17].

An infrared spectrum of the GCNF-HDA nanofibers revealed an absorption band at 1616 cm^{-1} consistent with the presence of amide bond linkages at the carbon fiber surface. Analytical data is consistent with a gross nanofiber composition in the range $\text{C}_{300\pm 200}(\text{NH}_2)_1$.

2.2. Materials Processing and Curing Conditions

As-prepared herringbone GCNF and surface-derivatized GCNF-HDA nanofibers have dimensions of 50 to 200 nm in width and 5 to 10 microns in length. The derivatized GCNF-HDA nanofibers were used as reinforcement additives to form nanocomposite materials. Both commercial bisphenol A type epoxy resins such as D.E.R.[®] 324, a diluted epoxy resin from Dow Comp., and Epon[®] 828 from Miller-Stephenson Chemical Company Inc. were used as matrix materials (100 parts in weight), and borontrifluoride-monoethylamine ($\text{BF}_3\text{-MEA}$) (Aldrich Chemical Company) was used as the curing agent (2.75 parts in weight). Blends of epoxy, curing agent and nanofibers were mixed at temperature of $90\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, sonicated at controlled power levels and duration, filtered to remove any residual large agglomerated particles, cast into a standard mold, drive out air bubbles at reduced pressure in a vacuum oven and then cured at $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for one hour and then $170\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for two hours, followed by cooling down naturally.

2.3. Instruments and Testing Methods

A Branson[®] Ultrasonic Cleaner 1210 (Branson Ultrasonics Corporation) was used to conduct low-power sonication. For this level, total duration of 60 minutes was applied to the blend of nanofibers and epoxy resin. A Digital Sonifier[®] 450 (Branson Ultrasonics Corporation) with an operating frequency of 20 kHz and a variable power output was used to attain high-power sonication. Sonication power levels and duration periods applied to sample blends of epoxy and nanofibers were the following: 15 watts x 5 min, 20 min; 50 watts x 5 min, 20 min; For all these high-power sonication processes, the tip of the sonifier horn was directly immersed into the mixture to conduct the ultrasonic treatment and an ice water tank was used to cool the reaction vessel.

In addition to three-point-bending tests, tensile tests and fracture toughness tests were conducted to characterize mechanical properties. Bending tests were conducted according to ASTM D790-00 "Standard Test Methods for Flexural Properties of Un-reinforced and Reinforced Plastics and Electrical Insulating Materials." An MTS 810 testing machine was employed to conduct bending and fracture experiments. The loading rate was 1.0 mm/min. The tensile tests were conducted on an INSTRON 5500 machine. The test was according to ASTM D638-01, "Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Plastics". The crosshead speed was 1.0 mm/min. The fracture toughness tests were according to ASTM D5045, "Standard Test Methods for Plane-Strain Fracture Toughness and Strain Energy Release Rate of Plastic Materials". A 5 mm machined notch was further cut with a razor blade in order to get a sharp crack with a crack tip radius of the order of tens of microns as shown in Fig.1. A Hitachi S-4200 SEM and a Philips CM20 TEM were used to observe the cross areas of fractured specimens.

Fig. 1 Experiment configurations for (a) 3-point bend tests (b) Tension tests and (c) SENB fracture toughness tests.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Bending Experiments

The nanocomposites with 0.3wt% GCNF-HDA and the diluted epoxy resin were prepared for bending tests. In order to disperse the nanofibers uniformly in the epoxy resin, the high-power sonication method (50watt X 20min) was applied to the blend of nanofibers and the epoxy. The flexural stress-strain curves of the epoxy and the composites without and with sonication are shown in Fig.2. It is found that the flexural strength and modulus of the sonicated composites have some degrees of increase compared to that of the pure epoxy matrix. However, the high-power sonication decreases the breaking strain of the nanocomposites. The results imply that this vigorous sonication might lead to the molecular structure

damage or degradation of the epoxy matrix. The effects of sonication conditions such as power levels and duration on the mechanical properties are major topics in this investigation.

Fig.2 Flexural property of diluted epoxy and the nanocomposites

3.2 Tension Experiments

To investigate the effects of different sonication conditions such as power level and duration on the mechanical properties of GCNF-HDA hybrid nanocomposites, tensile specimens of pure epoxy Epon[®] 828 (non-diluted) and a series of tensile composite specimens with 0.3 wt % loading of nanofibers were prepared. For the high-power sonication at power levels of 15 watts and 50 watts and duration of 5 min and 20 min were applied to GCNF-HDA nanofiber/epoxy resin mixtures using a digital sonifier to disperse the nanofibers throughout the epoxy resin. However, the resulting nanocomposite specimens showed no increase in the ultimate tensile strengths for specimens processed under sonication for 20 min duration at 15 watts and 50 watts summarized in Fig.3, which is similar to the bending test result [17]. By reducing the duration of sonication from 20 min to 5 min, nanofiber agglomerates appear to be well dispersed without incurring apparent damage to the epoxy matrix, and thus, the tensile strengths are slightly improved. These results show that more vigorous sonication does not improve the mechanical properties of nanocomposites and even lead to possible structural damage or degradation of the epoxy matrix. In order to disperse the nanofiber in the epoxy resin uniformly without damaging the molecular structure of epoxy matrix, the low-power sonication using an ultrasonic cleaner were employed. As shown in Fig.3, the strength of the nanocomposite processed using this low-power sonication is the highest, which shows that the power-sonication method is the best in improving mechanical properties, while processing techniques with high-power sonication for short duration also improved the tensile properties of nanocomposites.

Fig. 3 Tensile strengths of the pure epoxy and nanocomposites with different processing conditions

3.3. Fracture Experiments

Single Edge Notch Bending (SENB) tests were conducted to evaluate the fracture toughness of the nanocomposites. The results are summarized in Fig. 4 for the Epon® 828 system including the pure epoxy and nanocomposites with 0.3wt % and 2.0wt % fibers without sonication process. The nanocomposites with fiber loading of 0.3wt % show a small increase in the fracture toughness. The decrease in toughness in the nanocomposite with 2.0wt % fiber loading is probably due to the agglomeration of nanofibers without sonication as observed from SEM and TEM images. The fracture test results conclude that sonication is necessary to make the nanofibers deagglomerated, especially for the nanocomposites with higher fiber loading. In other similar fracture experiments on nanocomposite materials, no significant increase in fracture toughness was reported [18-22]. In a recent investigation, Rong et al. used inorganic SiO₂ particulate fillers in polypropylene (PP) and PMMA to study the mechanical behavior of nanocomposites [22]. The problem they observed was in agglomeration of the nanoparticles. They also observed that at high filler content the nanocomposite toughness rapidly decreased. Walter and Sholapurmath investigated the fracture toughness in pure polystyrene and their nano-composite materials and concluded that the toughness was governed by crazing [18]. Pure polystyrene materials showed large craze zones and resulted in the highest toughnesses while introduction of nano-scale reinforcements appears to interrupt crazing and results in less tough material. When clay particles are uniformly dispersed through the polymer a very brittle material results. Different processing methods also had significant effects on the appearance of microstructural features during fracture processes.

Fig. 4 Fracture toughness of the 828 epoxy and its nanocomposites

Actually, since applied load acting on the composite is mainly carried by the matrix and only partial load is transferred into nanofibers through interfacial shear, so it is not surprised that the strength and fracture toughness of nano-fiber composite materials do not increase significantly. This situation is quite similar to the transverse mechanical property of long fiber composite materials. For long fiber composite materials, longitudinal mechanical properties of composite materials are much superior than that of the matrix since applied load is carried by strong long fibers. However, the transverse mechanical properties are mainly governed by the matrix so they are quite close the properties of the matrix.

3.4 SEM and TEM Observations

Fig.5 presents SEM images of the cross-sectional area from non-sonicated and sonicated nanocomposite samples. There existed severe agglomeration of the functionalized nanofibers in non-sonicated nanocomposites shown in Fig.5 (a). After sonication, the GCNF-HDA nanofibers were dispersed more uniformly in the epoxy matrix as shown in Fig.5 (b). However, from any prepared nanocomposite samples, whether sonicated or non-sonicated, the good interface between GCNF-HDA nanofibers and the epoxy resin can be observed from TEM as imaged in Fig.6.

Fig. 5 SEM image of (a) non-sonicated GCNF-HDA/epoxy nanocomposites and (b) sonicated GCNF-HAD/epoxy nanocomposites

4. CONCLUSIONS

Systematic investigation of mechanical properties including three-point-bending, tensile and fracture experiments, of the new functionalized carbon nanofiber/epoxy composites were conducted in this work. Results show that there was only a slight increase (no more than 15%) in mechanical properties of the nanocomposites. In terms of processing techniques for the GCNF-HDA nanocomposites with highly polar pendent amino functional groups, an appropriate ultrasonication, a means used to well disperse the nanofibers, is necessary. Low-power ultrasonication is the best procedure for improving mechanical properties; while high-power sonication for short duration can reduce nanofiber agglomeration effectively and makes the nanofibers dispersed more uniformly throughout the epoxy resin.

Fig. 6 TEM image of GCNF-HDA nanofibers covered with epoxy

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